

Fokker-Planck Equation with Maxwell-Boltzmann Probability and $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_1+e_2)$

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The Fokker-Planck equation is a second order differential equation associated with a stochastic process, but if one seeks a stationary solution $\frac{dP}{dt} \text{ partial} = 0$, then it reduces to a first order equation linking $P(p)$ and $\frac{dP}{dp}$ with two functions $g(p,x)$ and $D(p,x)$ (drift and diffusion coefficients) appearing. If $g(p,x)=pC_1$ and $D=C_2$ with C_1 and C_2 being constants, one obtains a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution which obeys $P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i+e_j)$.

We argue that the first order differential equation with constant D and $g=pC_2$ may be directly obtained from $P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i+e_j)$ without using the Fokker-Planck equation.

Fokker-Planck Equation and the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

We use the Zwanzig Fokker-Planck equation given in (1) i.e.

$$\frac{dP}{dt} \text{ partial} = -\frac{p}{m} \frac{dP}{dx} \text{ partial} + \frac{d}{dp} \{ \frac{dV}{dx} + g(p,x)p \} P + \frac{d}{dp} D(x,p) \frac{dP}{dp} \quad ((1))$$

$$P(e/T) \text{ where } e = \frac{pp}{2m} + V(x) \quad ((2))$$

$-\frac{p}{m} \frac{dP}{dx} \text{ partial} = -\frac{p}{m} \frac{dP}{de} \frac{dV}{dx}$ and $\frac{dV}{dx} \frac{dP}{dp} = \frac{dV}{dx} \frac{dP}{de} \frac{p}{m}$ cancel regardless whether $\frac{dP}{dt} \text{ partial} = 0$ or not. This cancellation is like an ideal gas pressure balance on the two sides of a 1-dimensional box counteracting $\frac{dV}{dx} P(x)$ where P is like a density. In principle, the temperature could be changing in time so $P(e/T)$ also changes in time, but the mechanical pressure-force balance remains intact and the two terms cancel.

Consider seeking a stationary solution, i.e. $\frac{dP}{dt} \text{ partial} = 0$, with $g(p,x)$ and $D(x,p)$ both being constants. This leads to the first order differential equation (with a constant of 0 chosen) i.e.

$$g p P + D \frac{dP}{dp} = 0 \rightarrow gP + D \frac{dP}{de} \frac{1}{m} = 0 \quad ((3))$$

((3)) in turn leads to a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution: $\exp(-be)$. This solution implies:

$$P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_1+e_2) \quad ((4))$$

Starting with $P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_1+e_2)$

Consider starting with the relationship:

$$P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_1+e_2) \quad ((4))$$

Does this imply the Fokker-Planck reduced first order equation ((3)) with constant g,D ?

Consider de to be very small. ((4)) implies that:

$P(e/T+de/T) = P(e/T)P(de/T)$ but this equals $de dP/de + P(e)$ from the definition of a derivative.

So $P(e/T)P(de/T) = de dP/de + P(e)$ ((5))

$$P(de/T) = de dP/de / P(e) + 1 \quad ((6))$$

((5)) holds for any e , but there is no e on the LHS so $dP/de / P(e) = \text{constant}$. Furthermore, de on the RHS implies that $P(de/T)$ is also of the form de multiplied by a constant + 1. Thus:

$$P(de/T) = 1 + C1 de \quad ((7))$$

((7)) is the same result as assuming $P(e=0)=1$ which is fine because $P(e)$ is an unnormalized probability.

Using ((7)) in ((5)) yields: $P(e/T) C1 = dP/de$ ((8)) (equating de factors)

((8)) is of the form of the Zwanzig Fokker-Planck first order equation for constant D and g .

Thus $P(e1)P(e2) = P(e1+e2)$ contains all of the information of the Zwanzig Fokker-Planck equation in the case of a constant D and g .

One may note that ((8)) is an eigenfunction equation of the translation operator d/de in kinetic energy space. The kinetic energy translation operator shows that a collision of particles in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas may lead to one particle changing from one e to another. Thus the particle translates in kinetic energy space according to a probability function, but there is an overall constant in this scenario. The constant in the MB case is $-1/T$ where T is a temperature and it is a constant. $dP/de / P$ appears because this is a relative probability derivative. One measures the change of probability relative to probability because P may be unnormalized. This seems to be an information related result. Even though probabilities depend on e , temperature is conserved and d/de the kinetic energy translation operator acting on P seems to be associated with the idea of a conserved temperature. This seems to be analogous to the quantum mechanical case of $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle being a solution of the eigenfunction equation:

$$-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((9))$$

d/dx is the generator of translations in x , but p is a conserved quantity like $1/T$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the Zwanzig form of the Fokker-Planck equation for constant D and g values (which collapses to a first order differential equation from a second order one) yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution which implies that $P(e1)P(e2)=P(e1+e2)$.

Alternatively, one may start with $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_1+e_2)$, write $e_2=de$ and obtain the first order form of the Zwanzig Fokker-Planck equation. Thus $P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_1+e_2)$ contains all of the information of the Fokker-Planck equation for constant D and g , we argue.

References

1. Ran, G. and Du, J. Are power law distributions an equilibrium distribution or a stationary nonequilibrium distribution? (2013 or later) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1403.5441.pdf>